

SERVICE VARIABLES AND THE PRACTICE OF STANDARD PRECAUTIONS AMONG NURSES IN GENERAL HOSPITALS IN AKWA IBOM NORTHWEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT

¹USEN, OFONIME EMMANUEL; ²NTONG, MARGARET ALOYSIUS
& UDOFIA, INEMESIT ITA

^{1,2&3}Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Faculty of Education

University of Uyo, Uyo

¹08032706130; ²08163302948; ³08051904805

¹usenofonime95@gmail.com; ²ntongmargaret3@gmail.com;

³udofiainemesit0@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigates service variables and how they influence the practice of standard precautions (SPs) among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North West Senatorial District. Three objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses were created to direct the study. An ex-post facto survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was all 378 registered nurses of different cadres from the seven general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North West Senatorial District, with a purposive sample of 342 nurses drawn for the study. A researcher-made instrument titled "Influence of Service Variables on the Practice of Standard Precautions Questionnaire" was used for data collection. The said instrument was face-validated by three experts to ascertain the clarity and relevance of the items in order to elicit the required data. The reliability of the instrument was estimated using internal consistency, and a reliability coefficient of .82 was obtained. With simple linear regression, R and R^2 were used to answer the research questions, while F -ratio was used to test the three hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The result showed a significant influence of nurses' attitude, workload, safety monitoring system, hospital management support, and availability of resources on the practice of standard precautions. It was recommended, inter alia, that the health authorities of Akwa Ibom State Government should institute policies that make it mandatory to establish infection prevention and control (IPC) committees in all general hospitals and that the practice of SPs should be improved through regular training of hospital staff, especially nurses.

Keywords: Nurses, General hospital, Standard Precautions, Service Variables

Introduction

Occupation is a productive activity or service that one engages in and is regularly paid for to enhance economic livelihood and sustainability. Though it is a means of economic survival and a source of satisfaction, happiness, and companionship, it can also result in stress, dissatisfaction, and a threat to workers' health and well-being. The working environment or condition can positively or negatively affect the health of workers. In the same vein, the worker's health can affect his or her performance, productivity, and efficiency. The negative effect on our workers and working conditions is due to the prevalence of hazards inherent in the job. Meanwhile, hazards, as reported by Ugwu (2019), are seen as potential risks to the health of a person emerging from an unhealthy environment. A broader explanation by the Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety (2023) viewed it as any source of potential damage, harm, or adverse health effect on something or someone. Relating this to occupation, it can be said that occupational hazards are potential risks to the health of an individual from an unhealthy working environment or condition.

According to HSE Watch (2022), our occupational environment is the sum of external conditions and influences that prevail at the workplace, having a bearing on the health of the working population. The individual worker today is placed in a highly complicated environment, which is getting more complicated as man becomes more ingenious. The author also stated the three main types of interaction in a working environment to be: man, and physical, chemical and biological agents, man and machines, and man and man. Every occupation has hazards associated with it. In other words, a survey of workplace hazards shows variation as occupation differs and in accordance with the economic developmental stage, as well as the approaches to health promotion. Owing to this, there has been a deliberate step made to mitigate or eliminate these hazards with a view to achieving health and safety while at work; this is called 'occupational health'. This term, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2021), is an area of work in public health that promotes and maintains the highest degree of physical, mental, and social wellbeing in all occupations. This can be achieved using the approaches of disease prevention, safety assurance, and general health promotion. This practice of occupational health cuts across several disciplines, such as occupational medicine, nursing, ergonomics, psychology, hygiene, safety, and others.

Nurses are classified as Health Care Workers (HCWs) in the healthcare system, and they are an essential component of the system's equilibrium. According to the International Council of Nurses (ICN, 2023), a nurse is a person who has obtained a licence from the relevant regulatory body to practice nursing in their nation after completing a basic and generalist nursing education programme. Ugwu (2019) and

National University (2023) have mentioned a few of their specialisations, which include paediatrics, accident and emergency, medicine and surgery, anaesthesia, midwifery, and inpatient and outpatient care. According to Piai-Morais, Orlandi, and Figueirdo (2019), nurses are the most prevalent contingent in the medical field. This is because they provide direct patient care and are susceptible to biological exposures throughout healthcare practice.

Consequent upon this, the Centre for Disease Control (CDC) in 1996 introduced the term “standard precautions” (SPs), as it first appeared in their isolation revision, due to the difficulties and cost of diagnosing all patients for all pathogens before giving care, especially in resource-limited settings. The World Health Organisation (WHO) suggested that the level of precautions to be used depends on the nature of the procedure being done but not on the serological status of a patient (WHO, 2022).

Hand hygiene (HH) is a key element of SPs and one of the best ways to stop the spread of viruses connected with medical care, according to the Australian Government Department of Health and Human Services (2020). A risk assessment and the expected level of contact with blood and bodily fluids should also be taken into consideration when using personal protective equipment (PPE). PPE is defined by the US National Library of Medicine (2021) as specifically designed clothing worn to protect against germs. By lowering the likelihood of coming into contact with, being exposed to, and transmitting germs, this barrier helps protect patients and medical personnel from illness. Some of these PPEs, as listed by the author, are capes, gowns, masks, aprons, drapes, closed boots or shoes, goggles, and sterile drapes. This justification suggests that using PPE is a very effective method of protecting employees from working dangers.

Other measures, as stated by Infection Control Consulting Services (2022), are environmental cleaning, respiratory hygiene and cough etiquette, prevention of needle pricks and injuries from other sharp instruments, proper waste disposal, and clean and sterile instruments and equipment.

Despite efforts put in place by various bodies, strong evidence indicates that numerous developing countries, including Nigeria, still face crises in ensuring reductions in exposure to occupational hazards (Esu, Okeke, and Gobir, 2019; Nwoga, Ajuba, and Chime, 2021). This could be due to the extent of compliance with SPs. Service variables, as used in the study, are those variables that can positively or negatively influence the activities of nurses in their place of work. Some of these include the attitude of nursing personnel, workload, safety monitoring system, etc.

Nurses are bound, like other professionals, to a shared set of behaviours, values, and attitudes that are conducive to a professional environment (Kroning and Onuwumelu, 2023). It is noteworthy that one's attitude and behaviour become

contributing factors in a professional healthcare setting, which enhances a healthy work environment. Attitude in this context presents one's response or reaction to the principles of infection prevention and control or biosafety recommendations. Again, the amount of workload a nurse is subjected to can also influence the level of adherence to standard precautions. This can be as a result of the number of patients requiring the nurse's attention at a particular time. A nurse who is attending to multiple patients at a time can consider washing hands before and after attending to a particular patient as a waste of time, which would have served many other purposes. Carayon and Gurses (2020) added that increased workload is capable of reducing attention as well as giving room for errors and violations of safety protocols while at work. This also indicates that the amount of workload given to nurses can either positively or negatively influence their adherence to standard precautions.

Furthermore, every health care facility (HCF) is obliged to sustain the practice of standard precautions; thus, the management of these HCFs has a duty of providing an enabling environment where this can be enhanced. The responsibilities of hospital managers, as highlighted by George Washington University (2021), include, among others, the provision and development of an infection prevention and control (IPC) service, an occupational health service, and induction and continuous training on IPC for staff, equipment, and physical infrastructure. It becomes necessary that hospital managers live up to their responsibilities in this regard, as this influences the practice of standard precautions.

Finally, the availability of resources like running water, disinfectants, masks, gloves, and other protective equipment also influences nurses' attitudes towards standard precautions. In a hospital where there is no steady source of running water, regular hand washing before and after attending to patients becomes a challenge. This is in line with the work of Feyisa, Demisie, and Tesfaye (2022), who stated that nurses are always faced with the challenge of a lack of regular supply of equipment for clinical procedures. With this experience, it could be difficult, if not impossible, for nurses to adhere strictly to the practice of standard precautions. The absence of standard precautions can make health care facilities a source of infection and epidemic diseases for the community at large. In light of this, it is reasonable to argue that health care professionals' susceptibility to dangers affects how they apply safety procedures and guidelines and conduct themselves while at work. Based on this, the researchers looked at the impact of service variables on nurses' adherence to standard precautions when working in general hospitals within the Akwa Ibom North West Senatorial District.

Statement of the Problem

Nursing is an important occupation in our society, as professionals in this field have contributed a lot to the provision of health services to patients with different health-threatening ailments. However, the provision of these services exposes them to the risk of contracting various diseases. The prevalence of various communicable diseases makes this very possible. This calls for the adoption of measures that can protect nurses from contracting diseases while trying to treat or help others manage theirs.

The Blood Borne Pathogen Standard released by the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) in 1991 and the amendments in the Federal Needle Stick Safety and Prevention Act of 2002, as reported by Mitchell, Pannell, Arbury, Thomas, and Hodgson (2019) and Denault and Gardner (2023), require health facilities to implement engineering controls and the use of personal protective equipment (PPEs) like gloves, gowns, masks, goggles, and face shields as imperative to prevent sharp injuries and other exposures to blood and body fluids. This portrays the fact that nurses, like other health care workers, are obliged to implement all components of Standard Precautions in the course of their nursing practice, taking appropriate measures to avoid occupational exposure to bloodborne pathogens and body fluids.

Compliance with Standard Precautions (SPs) has been regarded as an effective means of preventing occupational exposures and infections. In the study of Donati, Biagiolu, Cianfrocca, DeMarinis, and Tartaglioni (2019) and Adesina *et al.* (2022), it was reported that there is increased evidence indicating that nurses' compliance with SPs can contribute to the reduction of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) among patients and healthcare providers while improving the effectiveness and safety of the care provided. However, this compliance level among nurses in Nigeria has been found to be greatly insufficient (Al-Faouri, 2021). In Nigeria alone, Nwoga, Ajuba, and Chime (2021) reported that needlestick injuries account for more than 18,000 new cases of hepatitis annually. The authors added that post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) is not well instituted in the country, and the majority of the workers are not vaccinated against the hepatitis B virus (HBV). The result of these exposures, if not managed, may result in loss of income by workers and their families, damaged careers and lower quality of life, employers' payment of higher compensation costs, excessive health costs, and reduced economic performance.

It is not uncommon to see nurses in the hospital attending to patients without the use of PPE like masks or gloves. This practice is worrisome as it exposes them and other patients to contracting infectious diseases. In addition to the disease burden, the functioning of the healthcare system may be reduced due to impaired working capacity, particularly in developing countries where the proportion of nurses in the population is already small compared to that of developed countries.

Considering the above facts, coupled with the benefits of safety behaviour in the nursing occupation, one would wonder why nurses should disregard the practice of standard precautions. Could it be due to their attitude towards this practice, workload, or safety monitoring system? This study is therefore being conducted to find plausible answers to the question.

Objectives of the Study

Though the main purpose of this study is to investigate how service variables influence the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District, other objectives include:

1. to determine the influence of nurses' attitudes on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
2. to examine the influence of workload on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
3. to determine the influence of the safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Significance of the Study

By using the results of this study as a first line of defence against the transmission of infection, nurses will be better equipped to understand and apply standard precautions, safeguarding themselves and others. With the help of their policy makers and other pertinent stakeholders, the government (local, state, and federal) will be able to create a framework for policies that will encourage the use of safety measures that will create a positive work environment, or "safety climate," which will control the spread of infections and lower the rate of death and morbidity.

To the Environmental Health Officers and other representatives of the Infection Control Unit of different hospitals, the findings of this study will encourage them to see the lapses created, thereby becoming more responsive to the needs of facilitating the implementation of programmes and preventive actions as well as supervision and feedback. This they can achieve through the production, pasting, or distribution of posters and fliers containing safety tips, respectively, the giving of early warning signals, proper monitoring, feedback recording, and follow-up. This will contribute to avoiding occupational exposures. It will also help hospital administrators and managers to be more proactive in the provision of adequate resources, as well as ensuring the proximity of these resources to areas of need for effective practice of standard

precautions in the care of clients and patients by health care workers (HCWs), especially nurses.

Additionally, hospital administrators and managers would work more closely with their hospital's enforcement unit in light of the study's findings to guarantee that all standard precautions that are relevant to their facilities are upheld. Lastly, the results of this study will broaden the researchers' knowledge on occupational health issues, particularly the adoption of safety practices to prevent and control exposure to workplace hazards, and serve as a repository of information for future research works on specialised areas of the Occupational Safety and Health Administration.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to guide the study:

1. What is the influence of nurses' attitudes on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District?
2. How does workload influence the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District?
3. To what extent does the safety monitoring system influence the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant influence of nurses' attitudes on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
2. Workload does not significantly influence the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
3. The safety monitoring system has no significant influence on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Scope of the Study

This study is limited to the following service variables: nurses' attitude, workload, safety monitoring system, hospital management support, availability of resources, and their influence on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in the seven general hospitals of Abak, Oruk Anam, Ikot Ekpene, Essien Udim, Etim Ekpo, Ini, and Ikono in Akwa Ibom North West Senatorial District.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation for this study is built on the following theories: behavioural theory and epidemiological theory.

Behavioural Theory (Geller, 2001)

The behavioural theory, usually known as behaviour-based safety, was introduced by Geller (2001). According to him, the behavioural theory reinforces incentives and rewards to promote the desired safe behaviours. This concept uses the ABC model, where A stands for activators or antecedent events, B stands for behaviour, and C stands for the consequences following behaviour. This theory is premised on seven basic principles (Geller, 2001, p. 30). These are:

1. The intervention focused on employee behaviour.
2. Identification of external factors that will improve employee behaviour (from the perspective of workplace safety).
3. Direct behaviour with activities or events antecedent to the desired behaviour and motivation of the employee to behave as desired with incentives and rewards that will follow the desired behaviour.
4. Focus on the positive consequences that will result from the desired behaviour as a way to motivate employees.
5. Application of the scientific method to improve attempts at behavioural incentives.
6. Use of theory to integrate information rather than limit possibilities.
7. Planned interventions with the feelings and attitudes of the individual employee in mind.

The behavioural theory explains both positive and negative attitudes of nurses towards the application of standard precautions (SPs) as safety measures in the workplace. The consequence of nurses' behaviour is C, while the application or non-application of standard precautions is B. The reinforcement or reward the nurses will get is an accident- and disease-free environment, which can promote the health of nurses and facilitate productivity. This theory is of great importance in this study as it addresses the behavioural patterns of nurses, which could influence safety in their occupational setting.

Epidemiological Theory (Abdel Omran, 1971)

The epidemiological theory holds that the models used for studying and determining relationships can also be used to study causal relationships between environmental

factors and accidents or diseases. It involves the issue of occupational hygiene, which concerns environmental factors that, if not addressed properly, can lead to sickness, disease, and other forms of health impairment. Epidemiological theory in this study is considered under the theories of accident causation and disease causation. The theory of accident causation has two key components, namely predisposition characteristics and situational characteristics. These characteristics, taken together, can either result in or prevent conditions that may result in accidents and incidents. Under predisposition characteristics are factors such as the susceptibility of people, perceptions, and environmental factors, while situational characteristics include factors such as risk assessment by individuals, peer pressure, the priorities of the supervisor, and attitude (Ali, 2023).

The epidemiological theory of disease causation, as analysed by Kent State University (2021), presented the epidemiological triangle, which is the traditional model for infectious disease. This triangle points out an external agent, a susceptible host, and an environment that fuses the host and the agent together. This shows that disease is an outcome of the interface between an agent and a susceptible host in the transmission-supporting environment of an agent from a source to a host.

These combined characteristics can cause or prevent accidents or disease conditions. A nurse who is particularly susceptible to workload (predisposition characteristics) is pressured by patients (situational characteristics) to speed up his or her operation, a decision that might lead to carelessness, and the result will be an increased probability of workplace injury. In another illustration, a nurse (host) prone to occupational exposures (agents) through the non-usage of personal protective equipment as a safety measure for any reason (environment) is at risk of being infected or affected by the agent that breeds occupational diseases in health facilities. This theory is useful to this study since it addresses, among others, the concerns of the causal relationship between environmental factors and diseases as well as the concepts of host, agent, and environment.

Empirical Framework

In the study of Zeb, Mohammed, and Khan (2019) on "Factors Affecting Nurses' Compliance with Standard Precautions in Resource-Scarce Settings," the aim was to determine nurses' knowledge, their compliance, and factors affecting their compliance with Standard Precautions (SPs) in three tertiary hospitals in Peshawar. A total of 199 registered nurses were recruited for the study through stratified random sampling. Findings showed the unavailability of resources like personal protective equipment (PPE), highlighted by 73.6 percent of the participants; workload due to a shortage of

staff by 55.7 percent of the participants; and 75.8 percent elaborated on the unavailability and dissemination of infection control policies as factors affecting nurses compliance with SPs. The study found a significant influence of these variables on the practice of SPs. It was recommended that PPE and other resources be made available and constantly in use, as well as the recruitment of nursing personnel and the development and implementation of infection control monitoring policies.

In the work of Nwoga, Ajuba, and Chime (2019), which explored standard precautions among health care workers in a tertiary health facility in Enugu metropolis, South East Nigeria”, a total of 200 HCWs—62 doctors, 92 nurses, 15 laboratory scientists, and 31 orderlies—were recruited for the study using Fisher's statistical formula. The research adopted a cross-sectional design. The results on attitude showed that 177 (58.5%) had a fair attitude, while 13 (6.5%) had a poor attitude. Reasons for not complying with SPs were mainly: unavailability of PPEs: 85 (42.5%); workload: 73 (34%); and emergency situations: 80 (40.5%). They recommended, among others, that the government should provide an enabling environment in the form of infrastructure and necessary IPC materials for the good practice of SPs.

Oh and Choi (2019) conducted a descriptive survey study that was cross-sectional on “factors influencing the adherence of nurses to SPs in South Korean hospital settings.” A total of 339 nurses were drawn from 9 general hospitals and 3 tertiary hospitals using a stratified sampling procedure. Hierarchical regression was adopted to examine the effects of three major factors on the adherence of nurses to SPs: respondents' socio-demographic, individual, and institutional factors. In the final model, the standardised coefficient attitude was the most influential factor ($\beta = 0.296$; $P.001$), followed by administrative support ($\beta = 0.171$; $P.05$), hospital types ($\beta = 0.167$; $P.05$), and safety climate ($\beta = 0.148$; $P.05$). These variables accounted for 26% of the variance in adherence to SPs. It was therefore recommended that changing nurses' attitudes towards SPs requires consistent promotion and a reward system put in place, along with practical training applicable to clinical care.

The work of Esu, Okeke, and Gobir (2019) assessed “factors affecting compliance with standard precautions among healthcare workers in public hospitals in Abuja, Nigeria.” It was a cross-sectional survey study involving 332 HCWs in clinical practices from 19 government health facilities in north-central Nigeria. A multi-staged sampling technique was used, and data was collected using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire and analysed using the chi-square test and logistic regression for the 332 participants interviewed. Knowledge was above average in 274 (82.6%), with the majority (76.2%) being compliant. Factors significantly affecting HCWs' compliance with SPs were IPC (0.167), availability of PPE (0.563),

organisational policy (0.872), availability of water, soap, and hand sanitizers (0.836), skin irritation (0.526), and interference with work (0.295). The level of knowledge, though good, did not directly translate into compliance, as the compliance level was average. Non-availability of PPE, other equipment, and a lack of regular training were factors found to affect compliance. It was recommended that HCFs need to build the capacity of HCWs on SPs through regular training and attendance of workshops; thus, the management of HCFs should ensure the availability of sufficient PPEs to enhance compliance with SPs.

The work of Jemal, Gashaw, Kinatic, Bedada, and Getahun (2020) was on "Clean and safe healthcare environment: knowledge, attitude, and practice of infection prevention and control among the health workforce at North Showa Zone, Oromiya Region." It used a cross-sectional study design standard, and a pretested self-administered questionnaire was distributed to 373 health facilities from 3 hospitals and 6 health centres, randomly selected through systematic sampling techniques. Multivariable logistic regression was performed to determine the associated factors with IPC practice, and a P-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. 55 percent had good knowledge, 59.3 percent had a positive attitude, and 48 percent had a good IPC practice. Positive attitude (AOR = 10.07, 95% CI = 4.82, 21.5) and availability of resources in the working area (AOR = 2.27, 95% CI = 1.18, 4.35) were statistically associated with good prevention practice. It was recommended that HCFs continue to capacitate their health workforce on IPC measures and equip HCFs with infection prevention materials.

Lowe *et al.* (2021) conducted a qualitative study on "Challenges and opportunities for infection prevention and control in hospitals in conflict-affected settings." Data were collocated as part of a larger service evaluation to access the context-specific barriers to implementing successful IPC programmes in these settings. This involved 16 hospitals in the Republic, South Sudan, the D.R. Congo, Mali, Nigeria, Labarion, Yemen, and Afghanistan. Respondents were ICRC-funded staff or staff delegate, 3 hospital administrators, 2 head nurses, 1 operational nurse, and 1 ward nurse/IPC lead. This mixed-methods assessment comprised a pre-questionnaire, telephone calls, a hospital questionnaire, and semi-structured interviews. The results of this study found that inadequate hospital infrastructure, resource and workforce shortages, staff education, and inadequate in-service IPC training and supervision are barriers to IPC practices in health facilities. They recommend, among others, an improved workforce to match clinical care in hospitals in order to avoid excess workload.

Research Methodology

The researcher-created questionnaire titled “Influence of Service Variables on the Practice of Standard Precautions (ISVPSPQ)” was used for data collection for the study. It was designed with a four-point scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) to rate items on the instrument. This instrument was validated by two experts from the Department of Physical and Health Education and the Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, respectively.

A purposive sampling technique was used, and a total sample size of 342 nurses was selected. Out of 342 sampled respondents, 326 were available and voluntarily participated in the study. As a result, a 95.32 percent response was achieved from the total of six HCF nurses who served as respondents. Simple linear regression, R and R² were used to answer the research questions, while F-ratio was used to test the three hypotheses at the .05 level of significance.

Ethical Issues

A letter of introduction and permission was obtained from the Head of Department, Physical and Health Education, University of Uyo and presented to the State Ministry of Health, who is in charge of the selected health facilities. This was to gain approval to conduct the study using their facilities. Respondents were duly informed of the research and consent obtained. Confidentiality was maintained as names were not needed, and assurance was given that the information gathered was only for research purposes.

PRESENTATION

Research Question 1: What is the influence of nurses' attitude on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District?

Table 4.1: Regression Analysis of the Influence of Nurses' Attitude on Practice of Standard Precautions

Variables	R	R ²	% Influence
Nurse's Attitude	.602	.384	38.4
Practice of Standard Precautions			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Nurse's Attitude

The result in table 4.1 shows the value of the regression coefficient (R) and its corresponding R^2 of .602 and .384, respectively. The R value of .602 indicates that nurses' attitude has an influence on the practice of standard precautions. The R^2 value of .384 indicates that nurses' attitude has 38.4% influence on the practice of standard precautions in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of workload on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District?

Table 4.2: Regression Analysis of the Influence of Workload on Practice of Standard Precautions

Variables	R	R^2	% Influence
Workload	.787	.619	61.9
Practice of Standard Precautions			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Workload

The result in table 4.2 shows the value of the regression coefficient (R) and its corresponding R^2 of .787 and .619, respectively. The R-value of .787 indicates that workload has influence on the practice of standard precautions among nurses. Also, the R^2 value of .619 indicates that workload has 61.9% influence on the practice of standard precautions in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District?

Table 4.3: Regression Analysis of the Influence of Safety Monitoring System on Practice of Standard Precautions

Variables	R	R^2	% Influence
Safety Monitoring System	.466	.217	21.7
Practice of Standard Precautions			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Safety Monitoring System

The regression coefficient (R) and related R2 are displayed in table 4.3 as being .466 and .217, respectively. The R-value of .466 shows that the safety monitoring system has an impact on nurses' adherence to conventional precautions. Additionally, the R2 value of .217 shows that the Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District's general hospitals' use of standard precautions is influenced by the safety monitoring system by 21.7%.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of nurses' attitude on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Table 4.6: F-ratio of the Regression Analysis of the Influence of Nurse's Attitude on the Practice of Standard Precautions among Nurses

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1620.969	1	1620.969	202.151	.000 ^b
Residual	2598.028	324	8.019		
Total	4218.997	325			

a. Dependent Variable: Standard Precaution Practice

b. Predictors: (Constant), Nurse's Attitude

The result in table 4.6 indicates that the F-value of 202.151 is significant at 1 and 324 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of nurses' attitude on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District is rejected. Hence, there is a significant influence of nurses' attitude on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of nurses' workload on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Table 4.7: F-ratio of the Regression Analysis of the Influence of Workload on the Practice of Standard Precautions among Nurses

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	2609.812	1	2609.812	525.471	.000 ^b
Residual	1609.185	324	4.967		
Total	4218.997	325			

- a. Dependent Variable: Standard Precaution Practice
b. Predictors: (Constant), Workload

The result in table 4.7 indicates that the F-value of 525.471 is significant at 1 and 324 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of workload on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District is rejected. Hence, there is a significant influence of nurses' workload on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant influence of safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Table 4.8: F-ratio of the Regression Analysis of the Influence of Safety Monitoring on the Practice of Standard Precautions among Nurses

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	917.000	1	917.000	89.978	.000 ^b
Residual	3301.997	324	10.191		
Total	4218.997	325			

- a. Dependent Variable: Standard Precaution Practice
b. Predictors: (Constant), Safety Monitoring System

The result in table 4.8 indicates that the F-value of 89.978 is significant at 1 and 324 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance. This is because the p-value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant influence of safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District rejected.

Hence, there is a significant influence of safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Findings

1. Nurses' attitude of 38.4% has influence on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
2. Workload of 61.9% has influence on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
3. Safety monitoring system of 21.7% has influence on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in General Hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Results from the null hypotheses:

1. There is significant influence of nurses' attitude on the practice of standard precautions in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
2. There is significant influence of nurses' workload on the practice of standard precautions in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.
3. There is significant influence of safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

Nurses' Attitude and the Practice of Standard Precautions

The finding of this study on nurses' attitudes and the practice of standard precautions indicated that there is a significant influence of nurses' attitudes on the practice of standard precautions in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District. The reason for the finding could be that nurses who attach importance to all the standard precautionary strategies are likely to adhere to the practice of standard precautions, while those who feel that the various precautionary measures specified in the standard precautions are an extra burden to their work are likely not to adhere to the practice of standard precautions. These individuals can choose to practice only those they feel comfortable with and pay little or no attention to others. This is in line with the words of Kroning and Onwumelu (2023), who posited that attitudes are of crucial importance in nursing as they help in the understanding of the point of view of people and processes in care and determine what they deem good, important, relevant, and appropriate. Also, as stated by Oh and Choi (2019), the drive for a person to take precaution depends on the

health belief, that is, the perceived threat of injury or illness, and consideration of benefit and cost. The finding of this study is similar to that of Rekiesso, Mengistu, and Wurjine (2022), who reported that attitude has a significant influence on adherence to the practice of standard precautions among doctors, nurses, and laboratory staff.

Nurses' Workload and the Practice of Standard Precautions

The finding of testing the influence of workload on the practice of standard precautions indicated that there is a significant influence of nurses' workload on the practice of standard precautions in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District. This observation suggests that nurses with an increased workload are likely to switch between works without adhering to the needed standard precautionary practices. This can be especially true in the practice of hand washing. Nurses with an increased workload can forget to wash their hands after attending to a particular patient before getting to another. This is consistent with the work of Carayon and Gurses (2020), who stated that when the workload is high on nurses, there tends to be a reduction in attention to safety procedures, which reveals conditions for errors and unsafe patient care. Similarly, violations happen when there is work pressure on the part of nurses due to emergencies. Nurses who are under this condition may not be able to follow the laid-down rules and guidelines of standard precaution. The finding of this study is similar to that of Nwoga, Ajube, and Chime (2019), who reported that workload has a significant influence on the practice of standard precautions among health care workers. Furthermore, the finding of the study is in support of that of Maitanmi *et al.* (2011), who reported that low staff strength, which breeds a heavy workload, is a barrier to compliance with standard precautions among health workers.

Safety Monitoring System and the Practice of Standard Precautions among Nurses

This study yielded important findings about how safety monitoring systems affect nurses' standard precautionary practices in general hospitals in the Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District. This suggests that nurses who work in hospitals equipped with a functional and efficient system for monitoring adherence to standard precautions are more likely to follow the different standard precautions that are appropriate for a given task. On the other hand, nurses in hospitals without a proper monitoring system for adherence to standard precautions are likely to show a carefree attitude at some point or attach less attention to it. It also suggests that hospitals that train their staff regularly on new trends in health protocols and follow up on their adherence to the training are likely to motivate their staff to adhere to the practice of standard precautions, which is also

needed to ensure compliance. The establishment of an action plan to address non-compliance with standard precautions. By adhering to the specified action plan, many nurses would stick to the practice of standard precautions in order to avert punishment due to non-compliance. The finding of this study is in support of that of Feyisa, Demisie, and Tesfaye (2022), who reported a significant influence of safety monitoring on adherence to standard precautions by health workers.

Summary/Conclusion

This study was conducted to investigate the influence of service variables on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Literatures relating to the variables of the study were reviewed under a theoretical, conceptual, and empirical framework. Two theories, namely, behavioural theory by Geller and epidemiological theory by Abdel, were reviewed within the theoretical framework. The meaning, components, and influence of the three variables of attitude, workload, and safety monitoring system on the practice of standard precautions were discussed under the empirical framework. Previous studies considering the variables in the current study were reviewed under an empirical framework. It was evidenced from the review that there was no study on service variables and the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District at the time of this study, hence the need for the present study.

A correlational survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 378 registered nurses of different cadres in the seven general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District. A sample of 342 nurses was selected to take part in the study using the purposive sampling technique. Data for the study was collected using a researcher-made instrument entitled “Influence of Service Variables on the Practice of Standard Precautions Questionnaire (ISVPSPQ). The instrument was face-validated by three experts: two from the Department of Physical and Health Education and one from the Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, University of Uyo. Internal consistency reliability was conducted for the instrument, and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. The data collected for the study were analysed using simple regression. The finding of the study indicated that there is a significant influence of the service variables on the practice standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-West Senatorial District.

Based on the findings of this study on the influence of service variables on the practice of standard precautions among nurses in general hospitals in Akwa Ibom North-

West Senatorial District, it is pertinent to conclude that nurses' adherence to the practice of standard precautions is influenced by their attitude, workload, and safety monitoring system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Nurses should adopt the right attitude that promotes standard precautions in the workplace in order to reduce the spread of hospital-acquired infections.
2. The government of Akwa Ibom State should provide adequate manpower and moral incentives to lessen the burden of excessive patient care workload, which reduces the compliance level of nurses to standard precautions with a view to making reasonable shift hours at work.
3. A surveillance system should be established for nosocomial infections by hospital managers to improve the consistent practice of standard precautions among health care workers, especially nurses.

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